

Deliverable D13.3

Machine-readable First Edition of the EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Catalogue

Project Title (Grant agreement number)	EOSC-ENTRUST Grant Agreement 101131056		
Project Acronym (EC call)	EOSC-ENTRUST		
WP No & Title	WP13: Trusted research environment blueprint - Establishing a common terminology and approach		
WP Leaders	Miikka Kallberg (CSC), Pål Sætrom (NTNU)		
Deliverable Lead Beneficiary	2. CSC & 12. UiB		
Contractual delivery date	30/11/2024	Actual delivery date	29/11/2024
Delayed	No		
Partner(s) contributing to this deliverable	CSC, HDR UK		
Authors	Miikka Kallberg (CSC) https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1457-3999 Rob Baxter (HDR UK/DARE UK) https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3693-8725 Stefanie Kirschenmann (CSC) https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2773-4798 Heikki Lehväslaiho (CSC) https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6263-1356		
Contributors	Pål Sætrom (NTNU) https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8142-7441 Monica Abrudan (ELIXIR Hub) https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0228-4353 Susanna Repo (CSC) https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3488-4767		
Acknowledgements (not grant participants)			

Reviewers

Heidi Laine

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6658-0664>

Anne van der Kant

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5802-7076>**Disclaimer**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. This deliverable is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

Table of contents

1. Executive Summary	2
2. Contribution towards project objectives	3
Objective 1	3
Objective 2	4
Objective 3	4
Objective 4	5
3. Methods	6
3.1 Deliverable scope	6
3.2 Spreadsheet	6
3.3 Database	6
4. Description of work accomplished	7
4.1 Machine-readable EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Catalogue	7
4.1.1 Conversion of TRE Provider Survey results	7
4.1.2 Clustering of fields	7
4.1.3 Catalogue schema	8
4.2 Cross-work package discussions	8
5. Results	9
6. Discussion and Conclusions	13
7. Next steps	14
7.1 Elaboration of use cases	15
7.2 Maintenance, sustainability and governance	16
8. Impact	17
Appendix 1. Catalogue schema	18

1. Executive Summary

The EOSC-ENTRUST project aims to create a European Network of Trusted Research Environments (TREs). One task in this 3-year project is to establish a machine-readable TRE Provider catalogue, listing available TREs and their respective capabilities. Towards the end of the project, this *EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Catalogue* (short: *catalogue*) shall be made accessible as part of the EOSC federation offering.

The catalogue will depend on service providers to populate it with detailed descriptions of their service capabilities to allow a comparative analysis of technical capabilities and identification of gaps between environments. The public version of the catalogue will give potential users of these services a tool to map their secure processing environment requirements to the available solutions.

In this report, we describe the steps taken to create the first edition of the catalogue (D13.3). This deliverable takes input from the first edition of the EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Inventory provided by the EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Forum work package (WP10).

The chosen format for this initial version of the catalogue is a spreadsheet. In the future, it will be developed for more detailed and technically advanced versions that will serve multiple use cases. The second catalogue edition is scheduled to be delivered in autumn 2025 and the final one in autumn 2026.

2. Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Create a European network of Trusted Research Environments, linked to EOSC and EuroHPC, to enable	1. A catalogue of suitable national or institutional TREs as part of the EOSC offering (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15)	Yes
	2. A ‘starter pack’ of exemplar projects to demonstrate how networks of TREs can address European research priorities (WP4/5/6, WP7/8/9)	No
	3. European researchers are aware of capabilities through communication and outreach events (WP4/5/6) and materials delivered to support national TRE training programmes (WP4/5/6, WP13/14/15)	No

transnational collaborative research on sensitive or restricted data.	4. Enable federated use via standards and technology for trusted researcher identity, data use and data access linked to developing European framework for trusted electronic identification of individuals (WP16/17/18)	No
	5. Enable researchers and software developers to deploy across multiple TREs via secure FAIR digital objects and workflows (WP16/17/18)	No
	6. EuroHPC capacity that meets the need for secure exascale and GPU (e.g., AI) computing can be identified and connected using the EOSC-ENTRUST framework (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	No
Objective 2 Trusted Research Environment providers implement, validate, and promote their capabilities through a European framework using common standards and shared legal, operational and technical language.	1. An established European network of national and institutional TRE Providers (WP10/11/12)	No
	2. A service blueprint that allows technical interoperability between TRE based on the EOSC Interoperability framework (WP13/14/15)	No
	3. National and institutional TREs consistently set out their capabilities with common representation for validated legal, operational, semantics and technical aspects (WP10/11/12).	No
	4. Define the security baseline and auditing procedures for TREs to support the Five Safes ¹ principles and capture requirements in guidelines for FAIR sensitive data in EOSC (WP13/14/15)	No
	5. Drive TRE composability via policy and process interoperability and set out an EOSC compliant governance model for a TRE services network (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	No
Objective 3 National funders and governments understand the network of TRE capabilities serving their	1. A machine-readable catalogue of TRE capabilities allowing detailed, comparative analysis of technical capabilities and identification of gaps (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	Yes
	2. Policy briefs on the capabilities of the European TRE Provider Forum (WP4/5/6, WP10/11/12) and Use Cases of their application in research domains of high societal impact (WP7/8/9).	No

¹ Ritchie, F. (2017, September). The "Five Safes": A framework for planning, designing and evaluating data access solutions. Paper presented at Data for Policy 2017, London, UK

<p>needs, and how TREs support their national priorities and their contributions to selected transnational programmes</p>	<p>3. Connection between the EOSC-ENTRUST Provider Forum and the European Data Spaces (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Objective 4 The European Network of Trusted Research Environments (ENTRUST) is embedded in the European Open Science Cloud and the European Data Spaces and fosters an ecosystem of public, private and joint-venture providers of TRE services.</p>	<p>1. National and organisational providers are incorporated into EOSC via national members and the European network forms part of EOSC long-term strategy (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).</p>	<p>No</p>
	<p>2. The emerging European Data Spaces build their capabilities on the network of existing and developing TRE providers (WP4/5/6).</p>	<p>No</p>
	<p>3. Technological developments required by one Data Space activity can be directed to a forum of TRE specialists, reducing the need for duplication and coordinating investment in foundational technologies (WP10/11/12).</p>	<p>No</p>
	<p>4. A driver project to demonstrate opportunities for public-private partnerships (WP7/8/9)</p>	<p>No</p>

3. Methods

3.1 Deliverable scope

Deliverable D13.3 along with this report is the first version of the Machine-readable² EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Catalogue. It has planned follow-up deliverables in the second and third year of the project (August 2025, and August 2026). The primary use case for the final edition is to have a comprehensive listing of suitable TRE/SPEs in the EOSC offering - stating the respective capabilities, tooling, access mechanisms, etc. - to allow comparison of the environments and allow choosing the right environment for the right scenario.

The first edition of the Machine-readable EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Catalogue is primarily based on a TRE inventory provided by WP10. The inventory contains the condensed results obtained from the 2024 EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Survey³, conducted by WP10, as part of their task to perform an inventory & summary of current TRE Provider capabilities (MS10).

Based on information gathered in the inventory, the initial version of the catalogue aims to recognise similarities and create shared categories of information based on the answers. Further iterations of the catalogue (years 2 and 3 of the project) will have an improved format which will finally be published.

3.2 Spreadsheet

The information gathered and analysed by WP10 has been summarised in a spreadsheet with columns containing the responses to different questions in the questionnaire.

To make the best use of these results, we used a spreadsheet format for the initial version, too, to understand and model the underlying similarities in features and compliance on different TREs.

In addition to utilising the inventory results and re-organising the information from the original inventory spreadsheet, we added additional fields describing TRE/SPE capabilities and categorised them. The schema of the spreadsheet can be found in the [Appendix](#).

² Open Data Handbook definition for “machine-readable”:
<https://opendatahandbook.org/glossary/en/terms/machine-readable/>

³ Laine, H., Campos, D., & Abrudan, M. (2024). EOSC-ENTRUST Trusted Research Environment Provider Survey Transcript. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12623607>

3.3 Database

For this phase of the project and the initial version of the machine-readable catalogue, a spreadsheet is a valid format. However, the aim is to convert the spreadsheet into a database in a later iteration. To facilitate this, data in the catalogue spreadsheet has been organised to allow for easier conversion: e.g. binary answers, drop-down menus, or reduction of free text answers.

4. Description of work accomplished

The main work was the compilation of the TRE inventory data into a more structured format. Collaboration with WP10 ensured accurate data organisation and WP13 worked on identifying commonalities and clustering information.

4.1 Machine-readable EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Catalogue

4.1.1 Conversion of TRE Inventory results

The first version of the WP10 TRE Inventory was compiled based on the EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Survey results and will be updated twice during the project. It was co-designed by the WP10 partner representatives, and also input from other ENTRUST WP's was invited. The survey was structured around the 5 safes, and based on an HDRUK survey⁴. It was modified to suit the needs of the TRE inventory information gathering. The survey included both multiple choice and free text response options that were collected as free text into a spreadsheet where each row corresponded to a TRE and questions were the column headers. This TRE inventory dataset contained information on 19 TREs from 12 countries exemplarily chosen by the Provider Forum WP, with data collected in 26 columns in free-text format.

We took these results, gave each TRE a unique identifier, identified distinct categories of information under each heading, and added new columns, which are further specified in the [Results](#) chapter. We took care not to remove any existing information during the formatting. The new columns were defined to include only one type of information. Where possible, answers were converted to binary questions, multiple choice, or links to external websites or resources. The results of the conversion work are shared in the [Results](#) chapter.

4.1.2 Clustering of fields

The 47 columns (old and new fields) were organised into different categories. In this first edition of the catalogue, the following 12 preliminary categories were identified, which will be discussed closely in the [Results](#) chapter:

⁴ Trusted Research Environment Technical Capabilities Survey <https://hdruk.github.io/TRE-Survey/>

- Identity
- Organisation details
- Functional capabilities
- Access mechanisms
- (Inter)national accessibility
- Accepted data types
- Auditing and security measures
- Computing and analysis services
- User rights
- Data discovery
- Federated analysis
- Architecture

4.1.3 Catalogue schema

The catalogue schema lists the categories mentioned above as well as the 47 fields mapped to these. It gives a short description of each field together with the values accepted. Furthermore, the schema indicates whether the field was copied from the TRE inventory (*copied*), derived from an inventory question (*derived*), or added as a completely new field (*new*).

The schema gives a comprehensive overview of the catalogue, which will provide a means for further discussion and assist in developing the current format into a database.

The schema can be found in the [Appendix](#).

4.2 Cross-work package discussions

This deliverable is closely related to tasks and deliverables of other EOSC-ENTRUST work packages as well as further deliverables of the Architecture WP. As stated earlier, the results of the *Inventory & summary of current TRE Provider capabilities* - a milestone for the Providers work package 10 - are directly fed into this catalogue. In addition, the WP7 (Drivers) gathered their *Initial Driver Requirements for TREs from the four Drivers*⁵ in August. These results were discussed at the First Evaluation & Adoption workshop in Helsinki⁶, September 24-25, 2024. With presentations from all of EOSC-ENTRUST's different work packages, the workshop provided a forum for discussion and alignment. One of the workshop's breakout sessions was dedicated to the capabilities of trusted research

⁵ Anne van der Kant, Jan-Willem Boiten, Milestone report M7.1 Initial Driver Requirements for TREs from the four Drivers [unpublished].

⁶ Kirschenmann, S., Kallberg, M., Repo, S., Sætrum, P., Azab, A., Balčirák, P., Baxter, R., Kulseth Dahl, P., Laine, H., Maccallum, P., Stansberg, C., Soiland-Reyes, S., & van der Kant, A. (2024). First EOSC-ENTRUST Evaluation and Adoption Workshop. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13860340>

environments, in which the catalogue, its contents and its relation to the survey were discussed in more detail.

In addition to the workshop, representatives from other work packages are regularly taking part in the regular and task-specific Architecture WP meetings. This ensures a continuous information flow between the related WPs. This report was also reviewed by representatives from Drivers and Providers.

5. Results

The deliverable has created the first version of the machine-readable TRE Provider Catalogue in spreadsheet format. It was shared within the EOSC-ENTRUST consortium, with initial feedback sessions organised to improve the format and start gathering content into new columns.

Below, the conversion of the TRE Inventory results to the catalogue and the applied changes are described in more detail. Listed are all the fields within their respective categories, including the original fields from the inventory, as well as the derived and added catalogue fields. In addition, the [catalogue schema](#) in the appendix describes the values accepted for the different fields.

Please note that this is the initial version and that the spreadsheet is meant to be a living document and category and field names might be added and/or changed, as the work progresses.

The most relevant changes done to the structure are described below, within the defined categories.

Table 1. *Description of changes during the conversion from TRE inventory to TRE catalogue*

Identity. A running number for an environment belonging to the catalogue as well as the name of the environment
<u>Fields:</u> ID; Name of the environment;
<u>Description of change:</u> The first step in forming a machine-readable catalogue is to have a permanent identifier (PID) for the resource and the self-declared name.
Organisation Details. Information about the organisation hosting the environment
<u>Fields:</u>

<p>Host organisation; Research Organization Registry (ROR) ID URL; Country code (two-letter)</p>
<p><u>Description of change:</u> The organisation's name is, e.g., due to language issues, subject to interpretation. An explicit reference to an open Research Organisation Registry⁷ (ROR) with more detailed information should help. A separate field with the country code makes clustering based on geographical distribution possible.</p>
<p>Functional Capabilities. Description of the type of environment and its main use cases</p>
<p><u>Fields:</u> Self-classification; GDPR role of the organisation; Service zones present according to the TRE Federation terminology; Dedicated to sensitive data or multi-purpose; Public description of the environment (URL); Available only for public benefit purposes (yes/no);</p>
<p><u>Description of change:</u> The self-declared description was amended by the choices to give exact GDPR role terms, the data controller or the data processor, of the organisation for the service. The functional role is further explored more precisely by asking the service to be defined using the three functional roles of TRE as defined in the DARE UK Federated Architecture Blueprint 2.0^{8 9}.</p>
<p>Access mechanisms. Information about how access to the environment is enabled</p>
<p><u>Fields:</u> Access mechanisms: Self-service User login; Access mechanism: Two-factor authentication (2FA) Access mechanism: Single sign on (SSO) Access mechanism: Comments</p>
<p><u>Description of change:</u> New fields were created to ask for binary answers for the presence of self-service user login, two-factor authentication, and single sign-on.</p>
<p>(Inter)national accessibility. Referring to the accessibility of the environment, e.g. can it be accessed from other EU countries</p>
<p><u>Fields:</u> From which countries can the environment be accessed? (Check GDPR terms)</p>

⁷ Research Organisation Registry <https://ror.org/>

⁸ <https://dareuk.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/DARE-UK-Federated-Architecture-Blueprint-Initial-Draft.pdf>

⁹ DARE UK. (2024). DARE UK Federated Architecture Blueprint (2.2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14192786>

Can the environment be accessed internationally? Comments: (inter)national accessibility
<u>Description of change:</u> A new field now asks for the geopolitical access policy statement in GDPR terms.
Accepted data types. Information on which technical data types are accepted for import and export
<u>Fields:</u> Supported technical data types in environment Supported technical data types for export Comment on data type/format
<u>Description of change:</u> Free-text answers are put into enumerated, multiple-choice lists.
Auditing and security measures. Information on security measures taken to ensure the security of the environment
<u>Fields:</u> ISO27001 certification (yes/no/in progress) Other security audits and certificates Tenancy isolation between projects/users (Yes/No) Security measures against unauthorised access Security measures for mitigating data loss Security measures for mitigating misuse by users
<u>Description of change:</u> The options for questions were made more strict and precise by disallowing 'N/A' and leaving only Yes or No.
Computing and analysis services. Computing and analysis services available for the user, such as information on the operating system, analysis software and tools available
<u>Fields:</u> Standard base operating system; Operating systems available to users; Access to HPC in/through environment; Computing power offered; Tooling provided; Support for AI / machine learning
<u>Description of change:</u> A simplified list of computer operating systems is available for users.
User rights. What rights and restrictions does the user have in the environment, e.g. can own packages be installed?

<p><u>Fields:</u> Are users allowed to import code/software/libraries (yes/no); User import source; User import size; User import type; User import connection; Conditions on users importing code/software/libraries; Measures against malicious code execution</p>
<p><u>Description of change:</u> Precise questions about current policy for users' abilities to import into the user environment: source, size, type, and network connection type.</p>
<p>Data discovery. Referring to the availability of a public discovery service for datasets</p>
<p><u>Fields:</u> Public discovery service for the data (metadata queries) Yes/No; Discovery service URL</p>
<p><u>Description of change:</u> A new category to ask for the existence and network address of public sensitive dataset discovery services associated with this service.</p>
<p>Federated analysis. Referring to the question if support for federated analysis is provided</p>
<p><u>Fields:</u> Support for federated queries Yes/No; Support for federated queries of metadata/data from external authorised users; Federated queries: comments</p>
<p><u>Description of change:</u> Two new binary Yes/No questions were added if there is any kind of support for federated queries and if these queries can be sent from outside the service.</p>
<p>Architecture. Free text description of the architecture the environment is based on</p>
<p><u>Fields:</u> Does the environment follow a specific reference architecture?</p>
<p><u>Description of change:</u> The architecture category was the only one where existing answers did not offer a way to formalise them. The answers were too sparse and varied to provide material for categorisation.</p>

The initial version of the catalogue was presented at the EOSC-ENTRUST Evaluation and Adoption Workshop, held in Helsinki on September 24-25th, 2024. During the event, the presentation generated a lively discussion among participants, focusing on the

catalogue's current structure, usability, and potential areas for improvement. Attendees shared feedback and proposed ideas for refining the format, highlighting the need for greater clarity, functionality, and alignment with community needs. These were taken into account as much as possible at this stage of the catalogue. The conversation also touched on possible next steps, including further iterations, stakeholder engagement, and timelines for the catalogue's enhancement to ensure it meets the evolving demands of the EOSC ecosystem.

6. Discussion and Conclusions

The first edition of the EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Catalogue lays a strong foundation for future versions. It facilitates comparative analysis of TRE capabilities and serves as a reference point for expanding the catalogue's scope. Moreover, it lists the first potential participants in a federated network.

The structured spreadsheet format used in the initial phase proved effective for basic data collection, organisation, and preliminary analysis. It allowed for quick input and sorting of information, providing a practical starting point for cataloguing relevant data. However, as the scope of the catalogue expands and the volume of data increases, future iterations will likely demand a more advanced and scalable database infrastructure. This transition to a dedicated database system will not only enhance data management but also improve functionality, such as enabling faster querying, more complex analytics, version control, and better integration with other systems within the EOSC ecosystem.

During the data collection process, some gaps and inconsistencies were identified in the survey responses, which could impact the overall completeness and accuracy of the catalogue. In some cases, essential information about TRE providers' capabilities, services, or compliance frameworks was missing or unclear, underscoring the need for targeted follow-up. Future efforts will focus on re-engaging with these providers to address these gaps and clarify any ambiguities. Also, providers who have not yet participated in the survey will be involved in testing the current catalogue schema.

This follow-up process will be done in collaboration with the Providers work package, as well as include feedback from the Drivers and Technologies WPs. Including perspectives from the other WPs is essential in filling gaps. At the moment of writing, the Technologies work package (WP16) is gathering requirements for the first iteration of the *AAAI for TREs Blueprint*¹⁰ and the Drivers work package (WP7) is refining their requirements for secure data environments from the perspective of the four EOSC-ENTRUST Drivers¹¹. WP7 is planning a blueprint validation workshop for January 2025 to facilitate further mapping between the Drivers' requirements and the Architecture WP's first-year blueprint (D13.4,

¹⁰ AAAI - Authentication, Authorization + Accounting and auditing

¹¹ The EOSC-ENTRUST Drivers <https://eosc-entrust.eu/drivers>

also to be published November 2024¹²) and to perform a gap analysis. All these results will feed into the next iterations of the catalogue as well as an updated version of the blueprint.

Strengthening cross-WP interactions will not only fill the current data gaps but also build stronger relationships with TRE providers, encouraging ongoing collaboration and future data sharing. Such efforts will be critical in maintaining the quality and reliability of the catalogue over time, supporting its role as a trusted resource within the EOSC framework.

In addition to having the catalogue publicly available on the project website by the end of the project, a more detailed version could be made available to members of the TRE federation, providing information relevant to the members of the federation, but not suited for outsiders.

7. Next steps

The first version of the TRE provider catalogue is a snapshot collected from actual practitioners in the field. Looking ahead, we will need to answer three key questions: Is it complete? How should it be maintained? How should it change?

To understand how complete it is there are two next steps: to identify how the catalogue will be used; and to plan for wider dissemination and engagement with providers beyond the project consortium. Deciding how it should be maintained comes partly from understanding how it will be used, and by whom, and identifying which other specifications or standards it needs to align with. The answers to these questions will shape how it should change and what governance arrangements, formal or informal, will need to be in place to manage that change.

7.1 Elaboration of use cases

The ultimate goal of EOSC-ENTRUST is to create a network where as much inter-TRE traffic as possible can be automated safely, securely and transparently. The key to enabling that will be the information recorded in the provider catalogue. For that, we must understand the use cases the catalogue must support.

Our initial analysis has identified two principal use cases for the catalogue:

1. A public-facing, human-readable version targeting research users who might be looking to select a TRE provider for their next research project. The researcher personas identified in the EOSC-ENTRUST Training Package (D13.2¹³) are a good

¹² Pål Sætrom, Heikki Lehvälaiho, Christine Stansberg, Haneef Awan, Ahmad Hesam, D13.4 - Year one version of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework [in review]

¹³ Deliverable D13.2 Training package for EOSC-ENTRUST Year one Blueprint & Interoperability Framework [in review].

reference for this use case. This version of the catalogue needs to provide enough information for a researcher to make an informed choice of the TRE partner, but at the same time not reveal too much technical information for security reasons. It also needs to be human-readable, requiring descriptive information.

2. A "service-facing", machine-readable version designed for other TREs and services within the EOSC-ENTRUST network to interrogate the catalogue automatically. This version will be important in building the required trust network between TRE service providers and is essential when we start to look at federated analysis patterns across multiple TREs. To send a workflow or other query from one TRE to another, the sending TRE needs enough information about the capabilities, data and security arrangements at the remote TRE to be able to reason automatically and configure its query appropriately. To enable a TRE to handle a workflow or query sent to it from another TRE, the receiving TRE will need enough information to decide on the authenticity of the query, whether the originating user is pre-authorised to submit the query, and whether the query is a match for the receiving TRE's query processing environment.

Our next step is to elaborate on these use cases and remain open to additional use cases that might arise. While doing this, we need to revisit the INFRAEOSC sister projects TITAN¹⁴ and SIESTA¹⁵ to make sure that we are all aligned.

One aspect to consider as well as use cases is external fixed points or constraints: what external standards or information sources must the catalogue take account of? This will be particularly important for the automated reasoning required in the second use case. Standard terminology for TRE-related concepts may well emerge through initiatives like Global Alliance for Genomics and Health¹⁶ or European Health Data Space¹⁷, and any constrained vocabularies developed by EOSC-ENTRUST must match these external standards if we are to maintain interoperability across the widest landscape. One option to consider is whether the EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Catalogue could, or should, become a specialisation of the EOSC Provider catalogue - an EOSC Provider TRE profile, perhaps. Therefore, if EOSC-ENTRUST joins and onboards TRE resources through the EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider catalogue into the EOSC Federation, the TRE resources need to be compliant with the EOSC Federation policies¹⁸ and the TRE Provider Catalogue profile needs to be compliant with the EOSC Profiles¹⁹.

¹⁴ TITAN <https://titanproject.eu/>

¹⁵ SIESTA <https://eosc-siesta.eu/>

¹⁶ GA4GH <https://www.ga4gh.org/>

¹⁷ EHDS <https://www.european-health-data-space.com/>

¹⁸ Currently being developed by the EOSC Tripartite Governance and described in the EOSC Federation Handbook, see <https://eosc.eu/eosc-federation-handbook/>

¹⁹ EOSC Profiles <https://eosc-profiles.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

7.2 Maintenance, sustainability and governance

The service-to-service use case for the catalogue means that it will sit at the heart of the EOSC-ENTRUST network, functioning as a service registry and common information source for all providers. Maintaining the catalogue becomes a key aspect of managing the whole EOSC-ENTRUST network. Further, "maintaining the catalogue" means both maintaining the catalogue's specification and maintaining the operational version that empowers the EOSC-ENTRUST network.

Currently, use cases tell us that we need two operational versions: an EOSC-ENTRUST private version with detailed service information; and a public version with reduced detail. Key questions to address in the next steps are:

- Can these two versions be derived from one common information source? Is the public catalogue a restricted view of the private one?
- In the core of the EOSC-ENTRUST network, the private catalogue needs a high level of assurance. Is the public version compatible with the security aspects of the private catalogue?
- If public and private catalogues are separate, how is information synchronised?
- Both could be realised as fully centralised, partially distributed or fully distributed services, with trade-offs in each case. Which approach is the best fit for EOSC-ENTRUST?
- Official federations like EHDS will need to maintain their own service catalogues. How to maintain synchronisation between them all?
- What are the costs of running the provider catalogue to the necessary operational standards? Answers to this question will be essential in understanding its long-term sustainability.

In designing how the catalogue specification must be maintained, we must consider how its integrity can be protected, how "implementable" proposed changes might be, and what the overall editorial process needs to be. This latter question quickly becomes one of governance and will begin to shape some of the technical rules of participation required for the future EOSC-ENTRUST network.

8. Impact

The impact of this deliverable is significantly contributing to increased awareness of Trusted Research Environment (TRE) capabilities across Europe and promoting a more consistent understanding of their role among key stakeholders. Moreover, later iterations will lead researchers and data providers to a clear overview of the TREs available thus assisting them in making informed choices. Additionally, it facilitates the establishment of a

common framework for TRE providers, ensuring greater standardisation and interoperability across regions. This shared framework lays the groundwork for more effective collaboration and alignment is essential for integrating TREs seamlessly into the broader European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) ecosystem. Making the catalogue machine-readable is needed for data to be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) because it structures information for computers to process, search, and analyse automatically.

Notably, the European Commission, particularly DG SANTE, has recognized the work of EOSC-ENTRUST as pivotal to the development of the European Health Data Space (EHDS) directive. EOSC-ENTRUST has emerged as a major stakeholder in the EHDS initiative, with particular relevance to the efforts needed for setting up Secure Processing Environments (SPEs). This acknowledgement underscores the importance of EOSC-ENTRUST's contributions in shaping data governance frameworks and technical infrastructures essential for secure, cross-border health data sharing and research. It also highlights the strategic role of creating a European network of Trusted Research Environments for sensitive data in driving European interoperability in sensitive data research and in meeting the data security and privacy requirements that are crucial for advancing the EHDS objectives.

Appendix 1. Catalogue schema

Category	Field	Field origin	Values	Description
Identity Running number for an environment belonging to the catalogue as well as the name of the environment	ID	new	PID: "TRES" + running number filled to four digits	Machine-readable permanent unique identifier for the service
	Name of the environment	copied	Free text	Human readable name of the service
Organisation details Information about the organisation hosting the environment	Host organisation	copied	Free text	Human readable name of the organisation hosting the service in English
	Research Organization Registry (ROR) ID URL	new	Unique string: " https://ror.org/ " + PID	ROR is a global, community-led dataset of research organisations
	Country code (two letter)	new	PID: "[A-Z]" + "[A-Z]"	Two-letter country codes in capitals according to ISO 3166-1 alpha-2 standard
Functional capabilities Description of the type of the environment and its main use cases	Self-classification	copied	Free text	Service self-description
	GDPR role of the organisation	new	"Data controller" "Data processor"	Sensitive data processing role of the organisation
	Service zones present according to the TRE Federation terminology	new	"TRE/RAZ" "TRE/DMZ" "TRE/DQZ"	The roles the TRE service offers as defined in the DARE UK Federation 2.0 plan: Research Analytics Zone, Data Management Zone, Data Query Zone
	Dedicated to sensitive data or multi-purpose	copied	"sensitive data" "multi-purpose"	Is the service dedicated processing only sensitive data or can it also be used for other types
	Public description of environment (URL)	copied	URL	Link to a web page with a public description of the service
	Available only for public benefit purposes (yes / no)	copied	"Yes" "No" "N/A"	Hosted projects must pass a public benefit test, e.g. as assessed by an internal panel

Access mechanisms Information about how access to the environment is enabled	Access mechanisms: Self-service User login	derived	"Yes" "No"	Break down of the original question to a binary answer
	Access mechanism: Two-factor authentication (2FA)	derived	"Yes" "No"	Break down of the original question to a binary answer
	Access mechanism: Single sign on (SSO)	derived	"Yes" "No"	Break down of the original question to a binary answer
	Access mechanism: Comments	copied	Free text	Additional comments
(Inter)national accessibility Referring to the accessibility of the environment, e.g. can it be accessed from other EU countries	From which countries can the environment be accessed? (Check GDPR terms)	new	"Access from other EU countries" "Only national access possible" "Outer-EU access possible"	Access limitations based on country or region taking GDPR limitations into account
	Can the environment be accessed internationally?	copied	"Yes" "No"	Possibility to access the service beyond national borders
	Comments: (inter)national accessibility	derived	Free text	Comments about accessibility
	On premise/private cloud, public cloud, or hybrid	copied	"Private" "Public" "Hybrid" "N/A"	Distinction between self-maintained and commercially provided infrastructure
Accepted data types Information on which technical data types are accepted for import and export	Supported technical data types inside environment	derived	"Plain text files" "Document files" "Spread sheet files" "Source code" "Images" "DICOM files" "Source code" "Binary	Technical data types or formats that are supported. Aim is to find possible limitations

			data inpropriety format" "Unrestricted" "Unrestricted. Export is limited to Principle Investigator only" "N/A"	
	Supported technical data types for export	derived	"Plain text files" "Document files" "Spread sheet files" "Source code" "Images" "DICOM files" "Source code" "Binary data inpropriety format" "Unrestricted" "Unrestricted. Export is limited to Principle Investigator only" "N/A"	Technical data types or formats that are supported in export. Aim is to find possible export limitations
	Comment on data type/format	derived	Free text	Comments about data formats or types
Auditing and security measures Information on security measures taken to ensure the security of the environment	ISO27001 certification (yes/no/in progress)	derived	"Yes" "No" "In progress"	The status of the ISO27001 certification of the service
	Other security audits and certificates	copied	Free text	Comments about auditing and security measures
	Tenancy isolation between projects/users (Yes/No)	derived	"Yes" "No"	Are project areas fully isolated from each other?
	Security measures against	copied	Free text	Description of security measures against

	unauthorized access			unauthorised access
	Security measures for mitigating data loss	copied	Free text	Description of security measures for mitigating data loss
	Security measures for mitigating misuse by users	copied	Free text	Description of security measures for mitigating misuse by users
Computing and analysis services Computing and analysis services available for the user, such as information on the operating system, analysis software and tools available	Standard base operating system	copied	Free text	Description of operating systems available for users
	Operating systems available to users	new	"Windows", "Linux"	Types of the operating systems available for users. Multiple choice
	Access to HPC in/through environment	derived	"Yes" "No"	Availability to utilise HPC in sensitive data processing
	Computing power offered	copied	Free text	Description of computing power, processors available or memory capacity
	Tooling provided	derived	Multiple choice: TensorFlow, Pytorch, Keras, Scikit, Custom-made analysis software, RStudio, Jupyter notebooks	List of common packages
	Support for AI / machine learning	copied	Free text	Description of machine learning related resources
User rights What rights and restrictions does the user have in the environment, e.g. can own packages be installed?	Are users allowed to import code/software/libraries (yes/no)	new	"Yes" "No" "N/A"	Ability of users to develop their user environment. Derived from the free text fields.
	User import source	new	"Clipboard" "Unregulated network access" "Network access regulated by TRE" "Network	The route of user initiated information flow into TRE

			access regulated by external entity"	
	User import size	new	"Any" "Limited"	Size limitation of user initiated information flow into TRE
	User import type	new	"Any" "Text only" "Source code" "Containers" "Data" "Explicitly no sensitive data"	Type of information allowed for the user initiated information flow into TRE
	User import connection	new	"Unregulated" "Encrypted" "Limited to stated internal addresses" "Limited to any stated address"	Type of connection allowed for users to import information into TRE
	Conditions on users importing code/software/libraries	copied	Free text	Descriptions of processes and conditions users are able to import artefacts into their environment
	Measures against malicious code execution	copied	Free text	Descriptions of ways the environment is protected from user and external actions
Data discovery Referring to the availability of a public discovery service for datasets	Public discovery service for the data (metadata queries) Yes/No	new	"Yes" "No"	Is there a public discovery service for datasets available in this TRE?
	Discovery service URL	new	URL	Link to the public discovery service
Federated analysis	Support for federated queries	new	"Yes" "No"	Are any kinds of federated queries supported?

Referring to the question if support for federated analysis is provided	Yes/No			
	Support for federated queries of metadata/data from external authorised users	new	"Yes" "No"	Are federated queries available from the outside?
	Federated queries: comments	copied	Free text	
Architecture Free text description of the architecture the environment is based on	Does the environment follow a specific reference architecture	copied	Free text	Any reference to an external specification for the TRE service architecture